

E-learning Education Problems Facing Nursing Students in Jordanian Universities During COVID-19 Pandemic Confinement

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: E-learning, Nursing, Problems, Jordan</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4718639</p>	<p><i>E-learning is a relatively recent and quickly expanding trend of nursing education, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, it is essential to properly recognize the problems and alternatives that prevent and enforce learning that encourages and facilitates nursing students' use of e-learning.</i></p> <p><i>Objective:</i> This research investigated e-learning education problems faced by nursing students enrolled in Baccalaureate degrees at four Jordanian public and private universities during the transition from face-to-face to e-learning education during the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p><i>Methods:</i> 260 participants from nursing faculties across the four years in 4 large public & private universities in Amman consented to participate in the study. They have been asked to fill A 30-item Likert scale electronic survey.</p> <p><i>Result:</i> While there are no statistically significant differences in the e-learning education problems faced by nursing students in Jordanian universities regarding the gender and year level variables, this means that the problem faced by female and male students in their different year levels is the same). There are statistically significant differences at ($=0.05$) in the e-learning education problems faced by male students in their different year levels.</p> <p><i>Conclusion:</i> This research revealed a correlation between the university sector variable and the number of problems experienced by students. Students in the public sector had more problems utilizing e-learning than their peers in the private sector.</p>

Introduction

COVID-19 erupted globally in 2020. Many sectors have been affected in different ways during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in health and education.

Government policies have accomplished a shared aim to reduce the spread of coronaviruses by adopting measures to limit social interaction. Teaching and examinations were suspended face to face (Motiejūnaitė-Schulmeister & Crosier, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic forced universities worldwide to move quickly to distance learning and adopt electronic learning.

"Electronic (e) or online learning can be defined as the use of electronic technology and media to deliver, support and enhance both learning and teaching and involves communication between learners and teachers utilizing online content." E-learning offers students "easier and more effective access to a wider variety and greater quantity of information" (Mooney & Bligh, 1997).

Nursing faculties in many universities had to decide how to continue the education process for their students efficiently. Professors, lecturers, & clinical instructors in nursing faculties have found themselves compelled to deal with e-learning overnight, although not all of them were prepared. The same has occurred with the nursing students, who have had to change from a model based on obligations and face-to-face learning to a model in which they will have to become involved in their learning.

E-learning is not new to learners. However, COVID-19 is reviving the need to explore online teaching and learning opportunities and associated problems. Luckily, a wide range of e-learning problems brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic is met by deploying multiple educational solutions a range of modern tools (Rodrigues, Almeida, Figueiredo, & Lopes, 2019). Using these tools, it is easily conceivable to modify content previously taught face to face.

However, other essential tasks in the learning process, such as clinical training and evaluation, can still be challenging without teachers being directly supervised, especially that the presence of nursing students in centers of health (i.e., hospitals, clinics) has been suspended in Jordan as well as in other countries (Jackson et al., 2020).

Consequently, to assist education and teaching authorities in allocating sufficient resources and reorienting university education for nursing students, understanding student experiences and expectations in the face of this important change is necessary. It is necessary to learn from those experiences and define strong and weak points to manage this situation in the immediate future.

This study aimed to learn about the problem facing nursing students enrolled in Bachelor's nursing degrees at four Jordanian public and private universities with the sudden transition from face-to-face to e-learning education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Literature Review

The ability to learn from anywhere is the clearest advantage of e-learning. Students will study at colleges and universities all over the world thanks to e-learning. Because of the Internet, distance learning can now take place in real-time. Teachers can use live video conferencing to meet with students who cannot attend classes due to time or distance restrictions (Srichanyachon, 2014).

Online education will help students because it is more flexible, accessible, and convenient; they will have more freedom to work at their own pace and time. Students who study online will also save money on transportation. Furthermore, the average cost of online education could be lower than traditional on-site education (Distance Learning Plan, 2013). Administrators will be able to lower the cost of higher education (Dibiase, 2000). Institutions will save money and resources, and teachers will update and revise their courses more easily (Hopey & Ginsburg, 1996; Owston, 1997).

Despite the clear benefits of e-learning, transitioning from traditional to e-learning is not without challenges. Time and demand for students and educators are increasingly rising, leading sectors to develop new approaches to providing a more personalized, self-directed learning experience (O'Doherty et al., 2018). One of the most mentioned issues is a lack of live, face-to-face interaction between students and instructors (Berge, 1998; Clay, 1999; Kirby, 1999).

Several variables might affect the success or failure of an e-learning curriculum, from student-led factors to managerial factors (Greenhalgh, 2001; Bediang et al., 2013). "Cultural opposition" between employees, for instance, was at some point established as a barrier to the commitment of students to technology-based training; hence, the implementation of effective e-learning programs may be crucial for personnel-orientated initiatives (Greenhalgh, 2001). Additional problems, such as time, technical matters, and organizational values, were conveyed in previous studies (Fish & Gill, 2009; Hartmann, Braae, Pedersen & Khalid, 2017).

Following extensive analyses of literature associated with problems of e-Learning, it seemed that various specialists classified e-Learning problems into four distinct metrics or subjects, namely problems related to students, problems related to teachers, problems related to infrastructure and technology, and problems associated with institutional management (Quadri, Muhammed, Sanober, Qureshi, & Shah, 2017). Yet, the problems discussed in this research are limited to students' problems using E-Learning.

To the best of the researchers' knowledge, there has been a dearth of studies that have addressed e-learning problems faced by students. Only e-learning problems encountered by faculty or instructors have been discussed in local studies. Research conducted by Aljaraideh and Bataneh (2019) addresses students' impressions of e-learning issues at Jerash University. The findings suggest that infrastructure is a substantial impediment to the use of e-learning at Jerash University. Furthermore, there are statistically significant variations in students' problems using e-learning based on gender and year level variables, with females and first-year students benefiting the most.

Previous research findings on local e-learning topics have been inconsistent and contradictory (Almarabeh, 2014). Almarabeh (2014) investigated students' perspectives on e-learning at the University of Jordan. The research revealed some intriguing issues involving Jordanian students. To begin, Jordanian students are well-prepared to use an e-learning system because they are aware of its benefits. The findings also show that perceived utility variables directly influence professed ease of use and students' attitudes toward using e-learning systems.

Mashhour and Saleh's (2010) research on e-learning in Jordanian universities, on the other hand, revealed widespread acceptance of e-learning in universities. However, several issues posed a threat to potential development. Inadequate infrastructure and a shortage of appropriate government and higher education administration support are among these concerns.

Al Adwan and Smedley (2012) also investigated the factors that could affect e-learning at two Jordanian universities. According to the results, the most important issues are the organizational framework and student technology skills. According to the report's findings, development and training are needed before adequately supporting the critical process of moving from traditional learning to e-learning.

Justification of Study

This study offers a future theoretical framework to elucidate e-learning education problems encountered by Jordanian nursing students during the COVID-19 pandemic and provide stakeholders at Jordanian universities with these problems so that preventive, directing. Remedial strategies can be developed to address them.

Research Questions

1. What are the e-learning education problems that nursing students in Jordanian universities faced during the COVID-19 pandemic confinement in lectures, exams, clinical training, faculty members, curricula, textbooks & technological gadgets for online education?
2. Is there any statistically significant difference in e-learning education problems based on University sector, gender, or year level?

Study Objective

This study aims to learn about e-learning experiences and problems faced by nursing students enrolled in Baccalaureate degrees at four Jordanian public and private universities during the transition from face-to-face to e-learning education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional approach has been conducted from February 7 to 21, 2021, as it is thought to be compatible with the objectives of this study. Through electronic survey in Google Forms (Google LLC, Mountain View, California).

Procedure & Method

The survey link was distributed through social media (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and the researcher communicated with participating universities to share the link among students in their respective schools. The survey was open to students from the first to fourth-year level. Participation was voluntary, anonymity was guaranteed, and consent was obtained at the start of the survey.

Participants & Sampling

Stratified simple random sampling has been applied to select participants (n = 260) from nursing faculties across the four years in 4 large public & private universities in Amman who agreed to participate in the study. Excluded from the sample were nursing faculty members and administrators.

Measurement

This study aimed to unveil problems facing nursing students at Jordanian universities during the COVID-19 pandemic. The questioner was developed for this study by the researcher. After a literature review, 42 were preliminary items generated to be included in the instrument.

Instrument Validity

The questionnaire was presented to a group of nursing lecturers to ensure its suitability to the Jordanian culture and ensure its usability.

The experts evaluated the content validity index of the questionnaire. They were asked to assess the items concerning the objectives and to provide a critique of the questionnaire. The experts determined the suitability of the questionnaire for this study.

The revised questionnaire consisted of two sections A&B. Section A is designed to gather participants' demographic data. Section B consisted of six subsections to measure the following aspects:

First aspect: The problems related to lectures,

Second aspect: The problems related to exams,

Third aspect: The problems related to clinical training,

Fourth aspect: The problems related to faculty members,

Fifth aspect: The problems related to curricula,

Sixth aspect: The problems related to textbooks & technological gadgets for online education

A 30-item Likert scale survey was used for measuring items included in each subsection. There were five answers to each of the items: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The results were converted into a triple rating scale to describe the values of the arithmetic averages (low/medium/high), as shown in (Table 1)

Reliability

The reliability of the study was checked throughout a test implementing on 30 students from outside the study's sample, with a time difference of two weeks. After collecting data and analyzing students' responses, the Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.88, which is acceptable for the current study.

Results classification:

The results were converted into a triple rating scale to describe the values of the arithmetic averages (low/medium/high), as shown in Table 1:

Table 1. The classification scale to describe the mean values.

Value	Description
1 - 2.33	Low
2.34 - 3.66	Medium
3.67 - 5	High

The previous classification categories were reached according to the equation shown below:

Class Width = Range (Maximum – Minimum) / Number of classes

Class Width = $(5-1)/3=1.33$

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed descriptively; according to the distribution, appropriate central tendency and dispersion measures were used. For Likert-style questions, proportions and percentages are used to summarise the results. According to the measurement level and underlying distribution, differences between groups were analyzed using student's *t*-test, analysis of variance (ANOVA), or chi-square test. The significance level α was set at 0.05. The data collected from the participants were analyzed to establish percentages, means, standard deviations, F-test (Analysis of Variance), and Chi-square using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version (27.0).

Limitations

This research only covers e-learning problems from nursing students' point of view during the COVID-19 pandemic confinement. Moreover, the research results might be biased because students with no internet access may not have received our survey, perhaps those seriously affected by the pandemic. During the study period, social distancing initiatives were implemented to avoid the distribution of questionnaires in person. The technical resource deficit reported is thus likely to be underestimated. Self-reporting prejudices may also have influenced the responses of students.

Also, there may be selection bias, as participation was voluntary. Students with strongly positive or negative interactions would be easier to join the bandwagon, eliminating more neutral opinions.

Demographic Characteristics

In section A of the questionnaire, the questions were concerned with collecting socio-demographic data from participants to determine whether the participants were a homogenous or heterogeneous group of Jordanian nursing students in terms of several factors. These factors were the educational sector (Privet, Public), gender (Male, Female), & study year level (first, second, third, fourth), as shown in Table (2) below.

The socio-demographic data provides an overview of the Jordanian nursing students who agreed to participate because they had a particular interest in the study area or who considered they could significantly contribute to the topic in this study.

Table 2. The demographics.

Characteristics	Variables	Number	Percentage
University Sector	Privet	180	69.2
	Public	80	30.8
Gender	Male	115	44.2
	Female	145	55.8
Year level	1 st year	57	22
	2 nd year	76	29
	3 rd year	60	23
	4 th year	67	26
Total		260	100%

The majority of participants were females (55.8%), and 44.2% were males. 69.2% of the participants study in the public educational sector, while 30.8% of subjects study in the private educational sector. 22% of participants are in the 1st year level, 29% study in 2nd year level, 23% in 3rd year level, and 26% 4th year level (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

To answer the first question:

(What is the e-learning education problems faced by nursing students in Jordanian universities during COVID-19 pandemic confinement related to lectures, exams, clinical training, faculty members, curricula, and textbooks & technological gadgets for online education?)

The means and standard deviations of the participant's responses on the items in each of the six aspects were calculated, and the results are shown below in tables 3.

#	First aspect: The problems related to lectures	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank
1	Poor internet access and connectivity.	4.39	0.68	high
2	Lack of technical support.	4.39	0.68	High
3	Lack of computer literacy.	3.52	1.02	Medium
4	Lack of discussions and interaction that stimulate students' thinking.	3.51	1.04	Medium
	Total	4.00	0.98	High
#	Second aspect: The problems related to exams	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank
1	Exam questions or instructions are ambiguous or confusing.	4.31	0.72	High
2	Insufficient time was allocated to complete the exam thoughtfully.	4.29	0.74	High
3	Lack of confidentiality and security as for the content and exams.	4.29	0.78	High
4	Frequent network malfunctions while performing the exam.	4.27	0.72	High
5	Suffering from anxiety or stereotype.	4.20	0.66	High
	Total	3.56	0.52	High
#	Third aspect: The problems related to clinical training	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Suspension of nursing students' participation in health-care facilities (such as hospitals and clinics)	3.90	0.72	High
2	Face-to-face monitoring and coaching are unlikely due to clinical training supervisors from nursing schools being denied access to clinical sites.	3.89	0.68	High
3	Increased risk of acquiring COVID-19 as a care provider is significant	3.89	0.68	High
4	Lack of the hospital staff interest in explaining the student's weaknesses and encouraging him/her to develop them.	3.89	0.65	High
5	Increase of clinical placement anxiety level.	3.85	0.73	High
6	Insufficient time allocation for students' supervision by hospital staff	3.81	0.72	High
7	The number or percent of trainees assigned to each department is limited.	3.81	0.72	High
	Total	3.86	0.60	High
#	Fourth aspect: The problems related to faculty members	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Inability to address course's intended learning outcomes	2.64	0.72	Medium
2	Inability to motivate students' participation during lectures	2.61	0.66	Medium
3	Inability to track students' progress effectively during their studies	2.60	0.79	Medium
4	Some lecturers are not convinced of e-learning value and benefits.	2.55	0.76	Medium
5	Lack of computer literacy.	2.53	0.62	Medium
	Total	2.60	0.50	Medium
#	Fifth aspect: problems related to curricula	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank
1	Difficulty implementing e-learning in certain subjects that necessitate clinical skills	3.90	1.01	High
2	Curricula are traditional and lack activities that develop students' creativity.	3.88	1.07	High
3	Integration between theoretical and clinical materials is not sufficient.	3.60	1.07	Medium
4	Poor e-learning course design.	3.53	1.06	Medium
	Total	3.70	0.97	High
#	Sixth aspect: The problems related to textbooks & technological gadgets for online education	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Infrastructure failure (software and hardware) and crashing systems	4.35	0.73	High
2	Online access to recent references and textbooks is restricted.	4.31	0.72	High
3	E-library does not fulfill the academic needs of students.	4.29	0.78	High

4	Inadequate mechanisms for discovery and access of library e-material	4.27	0.72	High
	Total	4.31	0.60	High

Table 3. Means and standard deviations of the participant's responses on the questionnaire items

The mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to lecture problems that Jordanian university students face are shown in Table No. (3). Given the total approximate mean value, it is clear that the problems associated with lectures ranked high (4.00). The averages ranged from 4.00 to 3.51. This indicates that the first study aspect items all considered problems related to lectures from the research participants' perspective. Item No. (1) "Poor internet access and connectivity." was ranked first, with a mean value of (4.40), while Item No. (4) "lack of discussions and interaction that stimulate students' thinking" was ranked last, with a mean value of (3.51). In total, two items reached high ranks in this group, while the other two were medium.

Table No. (3) also displays the mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to exam problems that Jordanian university students may face. Given the overall estimated mean value, it is clear that exam-related problems ranked high (3.56). The averages ranged from 4.31 to 4.20. This indicates that the second aspect items were all considered exam-related problems. Item No. (1) "exam questions or instructions are ambiguous or confusing" was ranked first, with a mean value of (4.31), while Item No. (5) "suffering from anxiety or stereotype" was ranked last, with a mean value of (4.20). In total, all five items achieved high ranks in this category.

Again Table No. (3) displays the mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to clinical training problems that Jordanian university students may face. Given the overall estimated mean value, it is clear that clinical training-related problems ranked high (3.86). The averages ranged from 3.90 to 3.81. This indicates that the third aspect items were all considered clinical training-related problems. Item No. (1) "suspension of nursing students' participation in health-care facilities (such as hospitals and clinics)" was ranked first, with a mean value of (3.90), while Item No. (7) "number or percent of trainees assigned to each department is limited" was ranked last, with a mean value of (3.81). In total, all seven items achieved high ranks in this category.

The mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to faculty members' problems that Jordanian university students might face are also shown in Table No. (3). The problems associated with faculty members were specifically ranked medium, based on the average approximate mean value (2.60). The average values were between 2.64 and 2.53. The thing that suggests the fourth research aspect's items all were considered faculty members related problems. Item No. (1), "inability to discuss course's expected learning outcomes," was ranked first with a mean value of (2.64), while Item No. (5), "lack of computer literacy," was ranked last with a mean value of (2.53). In this aspect, all five items received a medium rating.

The mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to curricula problems that Jordanian university students face are shown in Table (3); given the overall average mean value, lecture-related issues ranked high (3.70). The average values were between 3.90 and 3.53. The thing that suggests items from the fifth research aspect are all considered curricula-related problems from the research participants' perspective. With a mean value of 3.90, item No. (1) "difficulty incorporating e-learning in some subjects that necessitate clinical skills." Was ranked first, while item No. (4), "poor e-learning course design," was ranked last (3.53). In this group, two items received high rankings, while the other two received medium rankings.

The mean and standard deviation values for participants' responses to questionnaire items related to textbooks, technological gadgets for online education problems that Jordanian university students may face are again shown in Table No. (3). The problems associated with textbooks and technical gadgets for online education were rated high, as shown by the overall estimated mean value (4.31). The average values were between 4.35 and 4.27. The thing that suggests items from the sixth research aspect are all considered problems. With a mean value of 4.35, item No. (1) "Infrastructure failure (software and hardware) and crashing systems" was ranked first, while item No. (4) "inadequate structures for discovery and access of library e-material" was ranked last (4.27). In this category, all four things earned high marks.

To answer the second question: (Is there any statistically significant difference in e-learning education problems

based on University sector, gender, or year level?) the means and standard deviations were statistically calculated for the variables of the university sector, gender, and year level as shown in table 9 below.

Table 4. Means, standard deviations, and several cases for the problems of e-learning education from students' perspective according to the university sector, gender, year level variables.

Characteristics	Variables	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation
University Sector	Privet	180	3.32	0.61
	Public	80	3.64	0.48
Gender	Male	115	3.52	0.55
	Female	145	3.47	0.63
Year level	1 st year	57	3.44	0.51
	2 nd year	76	3.40	0.68
	3 rd year	60	3.62	0.55
	4 th year	67		
Total			260	

Table 4 shows a slight variance in the means of the e-learning education problems facing nursing students in Jordanian universities according to university sector, gender & year level variables. A Three-way ANOVA statistic was conducted to determine whether there are statistically significant differences in these means, and the results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Three-Way-ANOVA results of problems of e-learning education related to the university sector, gender, year level, and the interaction of these variables.

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
University Sector	3.43	1	3.43	9.80	10.0*
Gender	0.27	1	0.27	0.77	0.35
Year Level	0.50	2	0.25	0.71	0.44
Error	90.44	255	0.35		
Total	65.60	259			

**Statistically significant at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$)

The results of the study of variance analysis are shown in Table 5. However, there are no statistically significant differences in the e-learning education problems faced by nursing students in Jordanian universities regarding the gender and year level variables (which means that the problem faced by female and male students in their different year levels is the same). There are statistically significant differences at ($=0.05$) in the e-learning education problems facing nursing students in Jordanian universities regarding the university sector variable in favor of the private universities. These findings indicate that public university students faced greater e-learning education problems compared to private university students. This may be attributed to the large number of students attending lectures at public universities.

In their study titled "Study of Contact Barriers to Distance Education: A Review Study," Dabaj and Yetkin (2011) grouped the barriers into two major categories: the unhidden problems such as lack of technical knowledge, high costs of connectivity, and access to sites; and the hidden problems of resilience to emerging technologies, technological fear and a strong belief in conventional education. The current study findings indicate that Jordanian nursing students' perception of the e-learning education problems was very high. Technical problems are the most frequent in online communication, such as lack of technological infrastructure, lack of security, and privacy concerns students perceive the most. A result that agrees with the argument by many studies highlighted this issue. For example, Zolghadri and Mallahi (2013) suggested that the most significant issues related to e-learning infrastructural problems were low-speed internet networks, connectivity problems, and difficult access.

Panda and Mishra (2007) conducted a study to identify issues that faculty members consider when deciding whether or not to use e-learning in open universities and to decide that restricted Internet access, a lack of computer skills, and a lack of preparation are essential problems.

Johnson, Smith, Willis, Levine, and Haywood (2011) argued that poor infrastructure or any technical impediment could hinder the teaching-learning process. However, psychological, cognitive, and sociological barriers are minimal, and the students perceived fewer such barriers.

In addition, one of the problems that educators encounter in developing and implementing e-learning was a lack of expertise, particularly technical skills (Niebuhr, Niebuhr, Trumble, & Urbani, 2014). Inadequate computer and typing skills (Dyrbye, Cumyn, Day, & Heflin, 2009), as well as a lack of infrastructure, can limit lecturers' willingness or capacity to participate in the advancement or providing of e-learning (Dyrbye, Cumyn, Day, & Heflin, 2009).

Furthermore, lecturers are under pressure to take enough time to handle teaching, investigate and keep personal relationships on a work-life balance. In this case, insufficient time may be considered a major obstacle to mastering, developing, and implementing e-learning resources.

Perlman, Christner, Ross, and Lypson (2014) emphasize time as a constraint that faculties use an ePortfolio method. The faculty members had to spend uncompensated educational time because the pilot nature of the software did not provide them safe administrative time. It was recognized that it was vital that educators be allowed time to familiarize themselves with this form of the tool to ensure the efficient use of such a learning tool.

Conclusion

Efficient e-learning requires technical, administrative, employee, and student efforts. Higher education institutions should enhance e-learning by providing adequate training for both students and faculty members, provide financial support for upgrading technical labs, and promote curricula. To increase students' understanding of the value of e-learning, online orientation before their enrolment is required.

Jordan is only now beginning to integrate e-learning into its education system; further research is needed to improve this integration with traditional learning and to represent the reality of e-learning in higher education institutions. Indeed, this study recorded some of the students' problems and shed light on the process of e-learning at Jordanian universities, both private and public. This research revealed a correlation between the university sector variable and the number of problems experienced by students. Students in the public sector had more problems utilizing e-learning than their peers in the private sector.

Some of the problems we have listed are temporary and can be solved in the global health crisis. Others can continue or have long-term implications. These problems would not only impact the education and training of potential nurses without adequate action. Even the distribution of health services by the government may be interrupted on a broader scale. Many of these problems have become evident, and there are differences between subgroups that are increased due to the pandemic, mostly to the benefit of those with more access to resources. This creates an inequitable, although unintentional, learning landscape, and ensuring that this inequity does not persist the biggest challenge for stakeholders. Any actual or potential problems that might arise should be thoroughly investigated and tackled. Finally, global technological advances cannot be overlooked, as education cannot be separated from technology today.

Recommendations

E-learning has many problems in developed countries, especially in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic health crisis, and these problems are multidimensional and interlinked. Hence, nursing student needs assessment to recognize people with e-learning problems such as minimal access to technological services and fundamental needs should be conducted. Open communication channels should be maintained among administrators, educators, and students. Positive interaction opportunities with faculty members and students must be set up. Evaluation criteria should be consistent with desired learning outcomes.

Finally, students are likely to experience anxiety even under normal circumstances. Pre-clinical preparation, (digital) coaching, and assistance from their preceptors and supervisors are essential for preventing a detrimental effect on their learning outcomes.

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